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Ways to Prevent Conflicts in the Hotel Business

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Abstract: Ways and means of resolving conflicts in the hotel business are outlined. This thesis describes how to resolve internal and external conflicts in the hotel business, as well as the actions of managers and employees in their work.

Key words: hotel business, internal and external conflicts, the behavior of managers and employees, the role of foreign languages.

Introduction. Analyzing ways to effectively manage conflicts in the hotel business is important for everyone. Whether it's an organization or a hotel, there are always conflicts. The role of the hotel staff and, most importantly, the manager is invaluable in preventing and resolving these conflicts. Conflicts in hotels are studied in two groups. These two sections are further subdivided. The main conflicts are internal and external conflicts. There are various ways to avoid these conflicts at the hotel. Let's look at some of them.

For example: Managerial activity is important in hotels. Conflicts with a leader can be caused by the leader's insistence or misrepresentation. To avoid such mistakes, it is necessary to do the following:

- First of all, it is necessary to improve the managerial skills of the leader. Because a manager needs to develop relationships with his employees, his leadership skills, and organizational relationships. To do this, they must attend special training courses. If a leader attends such training courses at least twice a year, the leader's performance will improve, conflicts will decrease, and his experience will increase;
- Another important aspect is to prevent conflicts that arise through the wrong assignment of the leader.

To do this, you need to do the following.

The first step is to ensure that the tasks are performed by the supervisor. To do this, it is necessary to develop hotel regulations, which means that each employee must perform their duties based on their position. Once the hotel's charter is in place, all tasks will be sorted out. Conflicts can also arise if a manager assigns a task to an

employee, but the performance of that task is not part of that employee's job. Therefore, the leader will need to properly allocate responsibilities to prevent such conflicts.

Main part. There are also conflicts between hotel staff. In order to prevent such conflicts, the manager should pay special attention to the propaganda work in the hotel, as well as to the conduct of various spiritual and educational meetings with the staff, as well as the relationship between the staff.

If an employee has a problem, it is important to help that employee solve those problems. There are also disputes over the performance of duties in hotels. To prevent such conflicts, the following should be done. First of all, the hotel should create all the conditions for employees to perform their duties. That is, it is necessary to create all the conditions, whether technical or financial. It is also necessary to develop regulations for the performance of duties in the hotel. According to this regulation, the employee performs the duties assigned to him. In carrying out this task, the manager or highly qualified staff should not withhold their advice. It is also important to do the following to avoid organizational conflicts, which are another type of internal conflict in a hotel. Here, too, the qualifications of the staff are of paramount importance. The higher the qualifications of the employees, the different the attitude of the employee to the job. To do this, it is necessary for employees to improve their skills at least once a year. The employee will fill in the gaps in the training courses, which will help him to do his job well in the future. In addition, the manager must ensure that his employees feel responsible for their work, perform their duties conscientiously, act within their authority, and are subordinate to their employees. His skills and managerial activity are important in embodying such qualities in employees.

It is also important to prevent communication-related conflicts, which are another type of conflict. Such conflicts are mainly caused by the low culture of the employees, the mistreatment between them, and the excessive command of the employees by the managers. In order to prevent this, first of all, the hotel should hold various cultural and educational events and meetings. The activism of the leader is important in this. The leader must correctly explain to his employees the concept of "We are one team". It is also important that the older staff of the hotel gives advice to the younger ones. Because young people work on the basis of knowledge gained from older employees.

At the same time, it is necessary to prevent the command staff from commanding. Each employee must give orders and assignments based on their position. Conflicts are also prevented if ordinary employees follow orders from their duties in a timely and error-free manner. Another type of internal conflict that arises in hotels is personal disputes. Such conflicts are mainly caused by differences in the gender, age, occupation, position, and other aspects of the employees. To prevent such conflicts,

the following should be done. The first step is to improve mutual respect among employees. That is, the attitude of men towards women, or the attitude of older people towards a younger employee, or the attitude of an ordinary employee towards a manager.

For example, in order for the relationship between a male and a female employee to be good, it is important to ensure that the hotel staff is equal, regardless of gender. You also want them available to answer your questions when you are feeling uncertain about your suit. It is also important that the manager treats the employees. Because some employees try to be like the boss.

Another type of conflict that arises in a hotel is external disputes. These conflicts arise mainly with partners. For example, in order to avoid disputes over contracts and mergers, it is first necessary to properly analyze the contract between the two companies and perform its duties in a timely manner. . To do this, both the manager and the staff must work on a contract basis. This is where a leader's legal qualifications come in handy. For example, a manager may not do the job he or she is supposed to do because he or she does not understand the details of the contract. This leads to conflict.

It is also important to avoid disputes over the distribution of responsibilities that arise in the hotel. To do this, of course, first of all, it is necessary to understand the agreement between the enterprises and to know the tasks that he must perform. It is also important for the manager to be aware of the responsibilities that may or may not be included in the role of the enterprise. For this, the qualifications of the leader are important. There are also disputes over the quantity and quality of services in hotels. To prevent such conflicts, the following should be done.

First of all, it is necessary to constantly monitor the quantity and quality of services provided by the hotel. That's why the skills of the service staff are so important. The range of services is growing. In this process, it is important to improve the skills of staff. In addition, the quality of the staff should always be taken into account.

Conclusion. Everything in the service process, whether it is technical or not, must be up-to-date. For example: Whether it's catering, transportation, accommodation, we all need to increase customer satisfaction. Service hych time is determined not by quantity but by quality. Therefore, quality control is necessary. This requires more qualified staff. There are also conflicts between customers and employees at the hotel. To prevent such conflicts, employees are first and foremost required to be competent, polite, and responsible in their work. For example: If an employee is not polite to a customer, the customer will not like it and a dispute will result. To prevent this, explanatory work should be carried out by the manager to the employees. Disputes also arise because the employee and the client do not understand each other well. In order to prevent this, first of all, knowledge of foreign languages is required. If he does not know well, he should improve his knowledge in professional

development courses. In addition, the employee must take responsibility for their work. The role of the leader in this process is also important.

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